

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GENDER APPROACHES IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article covers the impact of gender approaches on educational effectiveness on the basis of statistical and scientific data, and the need to rely on the basis of the necessary knowledge for the ecologically sustainable development of women's knowledge, competence, entrepreneurship is shown. The educational process based on Gender differences and equality contributes significantly to the development of society.

Key words: gender equality, gender-sensitive, socio-economic analysis, national and universal values, social institutions, competence, entrepreneurship is shown.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ГЕНДЕРНЫХ ПОДХОДОВ В СИСТЕМЕ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. В статье на основе статистических и научных данных освещено влияние гендерных подходов на эффективность образования, а также показана необходимость опираться на необходимые знания для экологически устойчивого развития женских знаний, компетентности, предпринимательства. Образовательный процесс, основанный на гендерных различиях и равенстве, вносит значительный вклад в развитие общества.

Ключевые слова: гендерное равенство, гендерная чувствительность, социально-экономический анализ, национальные и общечеловеческие ценности, социальные институты, компетентность, предпринимательство.

OLIV TA'LIM TIZIMIDA GENDER YONDASHUVLARINING SAMARADORLIGI

Annotatsiya. Maqolada statistik va ilmiy ma'lumotlarga asoslanib, gender yondashuvlarining ta'lim samaradorligiga ta'siri ko'rsatilgan, shuningdek, ayollar bilimi, malakasi va tadbirkorligini ekologik jihatdan barqaror rivojlantirish uchun kerakli bilimlarga tayanish zarurligi ko'rsatilgan. Gender farqlari va tenglikka asoslangan ta'lim jarayoni jamiyat rivojiga katta hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: gender tenglik, gender xabardorlik, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy tahlil, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlar, ijtimoiy institutlar, kompetentsiya, tadbirkorlik.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is not surprising that the information age of the 21st century is recognized as such. Nogaku believes that society develops and finds progress, relying on the knowledge and entrepreneurship of the individual. And the educational process, organized on the basis of Gender differences and equality, makes an important contribution to the development of society, it will be able to field as a necessary component of the cultural, socio-economic and environmentally sustainable development of the pupil's personality.

In our country, by the end of the last century, thoughts about gender differences and similarities in the educational process began to be put forward. The fact is that gender is an approach that has arisen as a continuation of feminist theory.

At the conference of UNESCO on October 9, 1998, it was recognized that the purpose of the higher education system is the restoration of society free from violence and oppression. It is noted that in order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to re-develop educational programs using new pedagogical technologies and modern methods. In the newly developed training programs, equality of men and women, as well as gender factors of all subjects were taken into account. These initial attempts, based on world practice, were supported by the UN Development Programme, UNESCO, the Open Society Foundation. As a result, the course of gender studies was introduced into the programs of Moscow State University, Kharkiv University and a number of higher educational institutions of the CIS countries. Materials of the special session of the UN General Assembly on the theme of "women-2000: gender equality, development and peace" in 2000, recent studies prepared by the World Bank indicate that there is an inalienable link between economic development and gender equality. Experiments in this regard have shown that students' interest in gender Research is strong¹.

II. THE MAIN PART

The study of

gender studies in higher educational institutions of our republic is not only the formation of the future thinking of specialists on the basis of the latest analytical achievements in the world, but also the promotion of further development of this sphere in the science of Uzbekistan, undoubtedly. Gender differences and similarities are based on taking into account the similarities and differences in the educational activities of girls and boys in the educational process. This, in turn, will help to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process. He or she determines the im- cones of the pupil's personality of this gender.

The concept of "Gender " primarily covers the socio-psychological and pedagogical aspects of the relationship between a man and a woman, a boy and a girl. This concept is connected with new social views and culture. Gender conception is developing in the CIS region as a category of socio-economic analysis. Currently, a number of achievements have been achieved in the implementation of the gender Research course in Russia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Ukraine and other republics of the former Union to the educational programs of higher education institutions. One of the most important achievements in pedagogical science today is the opening of opportunities for teaching on the basis of gender equality and differences. This phenomenon also has a special value in terms of humanization of Education.

III. DISCUSSION

The problem of Gender attracts the attention of philosophers, sociologists, anthropologists, linguists, literary critics, psychologists and educators. The psychological aspects of gender are well-known psychologists Z. Freud, T. Parsons, R. Staller, Sh. Bern, A. Bandura, Simona de Beaver, A. Klima, S. Mining, A. Usmanova, I.S. Klesina, E. Gaziev, O.Abdusattorova, X. R Haydarova, sociological aspects E.Goffman, R.Xaf, A.Kolstkorova, A. Zdravomislova, A.A. Tyomkina, G.K. Zaitsev and A.G. Zaitsev, G.B. Urazalieva, philosophical aspects of Keith West, D. Zimmerman, S.G. Ayzavova, I. Jerebkinas, aspects related to anthropology E.RYarskaya-

¹ Ismailova, Z., Choriev, R., Musurmanova, A., & Aripjanova, M. (2020). Methods of training of teachers of university on advanced training courses. *Journal of Critical Reviews*. Innovare Academics Sciences Pvt. Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.05.85>
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Smirnova, some aspects of pedagogy L. Shustova, P. Repkina, R. Safarova, G. Lit up in the works of Akramova.

The educational system is of particular importance in society not only as a factor of technological and socio-economic development, but also as an important strategic tool for spiritual and economic development. Therefore, in our independent country, great attention is paid to the sphere of education every year. This task is entrusted to all stages of the educational system: from pre-school educational institutions to the higher stages of Higher Education².

Despite the variety of approaches and points of view in relation to the designation of gender, it is possible to distinguish two concepts. These conceptions are as follows:

- 1) gender social structure theory;
- 2) gender system theory.

The approach to gender from a social point of view will be as follows: from a biological point of view, gender is a set of tasks that are inherent in a particular society to the gender that is decided on, and the specific behavior of both the boy and the girl children, the different manifestations associated with the social norms of interaction.

The concept of interaction between boys and girls is called R. Introduced by Hof, the boy and the girl represent the spiritual and cultural images of children. In accordance with this approach, gender is represented as a measure of the social relationships that are decided in a particular society. The study of socio-humanities by students in the higher education system promotes the development of social activity of student-girls on the basis of gender approach.

Gender stratification is the basis of the development of the socio-pedagogical system of humanism in society and education system. At present, the social activist of students and students-girls of social institutes in society such as family, education, religion, culture-educational importance in the development of gini increases the effectiveness of this process. One of the most important achievements in pedagogical science today is the opening of opportunities for teaching on the basis of gender equality and differences.

IV. CONCLUSIONS:

The reforms carried out in the Republic are giving positive results in the economic, social, political, cultural and educational development of our society among the most developed countries of the world. Such changes are carried out consistently in the educational system, as in all spheres. At present, radical changes are taking place in the socio-economic and spiritual life of Uzbekistan, the issue of organizing the educational process on the basis of gender equality and differences of the individual should also become a component of pedagogical processes and research. With the help of the educational materials provided taking into account Gender equality and differences, students' observability, design, hypothesis, prediction skills are consistently formulated. After all, the regulation of social and educational relations between girls and boys has an important pedagogical significance. Because training through its processes, social relations between male and female members of society are decided in perspective.

²Karabaevna, Z., & Raximovich, B. (2019). The use of innovation technologies in the formation of students' professional competences. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 9(1), 6898–6902. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.A2996.109119>

² Hof R. The emergence and development of gender studies. / *Gender, tender, culture.* // Ed. by E. Schore K. Haider. - M.: 1999. - pp. 23-53.

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